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Abstract

The purpose of this report is to introduce the reader to key concepts of fibre optic sensing often referred to as DAS (Distributed Acoustic Sensing). The DAS field laboratory in Svalbard is presented and several examples of various recordings ranging from whale calls to earthquakes and ocean gravity waves are presented and discussed with respect to coupling and signal effects.

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Executive Summary

Our DAS-laboratory at Svalbard includes two 256 km long fibre optic cables connecting Ny-Ålesund to Longyearbyen. When sediments are present at the seabed, the cables are trenched approximately a metre below seabed. This offers a unique possibility to study coupling effects related to trenching, since the cable is both laid directly on the seabed and trenched. We find that for seismic energy coming from below, as for instance earthquakes, there is a significant difference in signal strength to the DAS-fibre, depending on whether the cable is trenched or not. For earthquakes, the coupling is not zero for the areas where the cable is laid directly on bedrock, but much weaker. In addition to this we see significant variations related to the thickness of the sediment column. We find that much more energy is trapped in the sediment layer when it is thick, leading to higher RMS-values for the DAS-data in such areas.

A dedicated test using a small air gun source fired at 3.5 m depth, shows that there is a non-zero DAS signal at zero offset. We suggest a phenomenological equation to explain that this is related to the gaugelength and maybe also bending effects impacting the signal at zero offset. For some areas at large offsets, we observe Scholte waves that occur prior to the direct P-wave arrival, and this is interpreted as a head-wave (refracted wave at the interface between the sediment layer and the bedrock) generating a Scholte wave when the headwave hits an inhomogeneity at the seabed (could be an icescour or glacial depression at the seabed). This is rarely observed and is a very interesting observation, since it can give valuable information about the top layer/sediment layer.

Our analysis is restricted to cable lengths up to 100 km. We limited our analysis to this length since we reach the limits of our optical budget. This is related to the use of a small gauge length. This gives a high spatial resolution but limits the dynamic range. Additionally, we use a standard G652(d), with a 0.18dB/km loss. A G654 ultra-low loss fibre with a 0.16dB/km loss combined with a larger gauge length could extend the range up to 150 km. However, for ultralong seabed cables (more than 1000 km) there is a need for DAS-repeaters. This is briefly discussed in this report, referring to some promising tests done in the laboratory. For calibration and separating temperature effects from current effects, we propose to measure the temperature in the fibre simultaneously with DAS-measurements, often referred to as DTS-measurements. A short discussion of various types of DTS-measurements is presented.

Since the DAS data acquired from the fibre optic cables offshore Svalbard is sensitive due to protection of Norwegian national infrastructure, we have implemented a strict procedure prior to releasing data. All data presented in this report have been checked and approved prior to publication.

1 Introduction

1.1 Principles of DAS acquisition

Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS)

The principle of distributed acoustic sensing using a conventional telecommunication fibre is shown in Figure 1. An interrogator emits a sequence or a sweep of optical laser signals into the fibre. Typical wavelengths for the sweep optical signals are around 1550 nm, and the gauge length has been varied between 4 and 8 m during the recording phase. Typical temporal bandwidth is 300 Hz. When an acoustic or seismic wave hits the fibre it will be strained and this strain can be measured very accurately by the interrogator and in this way the acoustic signal is transformed into a strain that can be measured by the interrogator. Since the speed of light in the fibre is known, it is also possible to determine exactly where the strain signal hit the cable. In this way one might say that a telecommunication fibre is a long antenna containing several thousand channels with dense temporal sampling for each channel; very similar to seismic streamers towed behind a vessel. The use of DAS has increased significantly during the last decade and includes a lot of various applications such as earthquake detection, avalanche detection, whale detection, monitoring of temperature changes, oceanographic studies and environmental monitoring including wind, waves and road traffic.

Figure 1.1: Schematic view of DAS-acquisition of acoustic signals in a fibre optic cable.

The interrogator measure the time derivative of phase changes, and the following equation is used to compute the strain rate along the fibre assuming that the phase rate change ($\Delta\dot{\phi}$) is measured (Waagaard et al., 2021):

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{xx} = \frac{\lambda_0}{4\pi n \zeta G} \Delta\dot{\phi} \quad (1)$$

Where $\dot{\varepsilon}_{xx}$ is the time derivative of the axial strain in the fibre, λ_0 the wavelength of the laser light (1550 nm), n the refraction index of the glass in the fibre (1.476), ζ the photo-elastic coefficient and G the gaugelength.

Then, the strain can be computed by integrating the strain rate over time. So far we have neglected temperature changes. If temperature changes occur, then the length of the fibre will change as well as the refraction index (Bradley et al., 2023):

$$\Delta\phi = \phi \left(\varepsilon_{xx} + \frac{\Delta n}{n} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta\phi = \phi \Delta T (\alpha_T + \xi) \quad (3)$$

Where T is temperature, $\alpha_T = \frac{1}{L} \frac{dL}{dT}$ is the thermal expansion coefficient and $\xi = \frac{1}{n} \frac{dn}{dT}$ is the thermal optic coefficient. Typical values for these two coefficients are $0.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$, respectively. We observe from equation 3 that temperature changes will imply strain changes (similar to a railway that is expanding under sun heat) as well as changes in the refractive index (change in velocity of light in the fibre). This means that when we measure the time derivative of phase changes, our measurements are sensitive to both strain changes as well as temperature changes. Bradley et al. 2023 demonstrates how the above equations can be used to estimate temperature changes caused by for instance injection of cold water into a warmer hydrocarbon reservoir. For the remaining part of this report we will assume that we measure strain rate in our experiments, and hence we neglect the temperature effect.

1.2 Directivity effects

Since the fibre measures horizontal strain, an acoustic wave hitting the fibre at normal incidence will normally lead to zero DAS-signal. Figure 2 below illustrates this effect where several fin calls have been

recorded at one of the Svalbard cables. We notice that for a whale close to the fibre (to the left) there is a small gap in signal at the apex. When the crossline distance between the whale and the fibre is larger (calls to the right in Figure 2) this gap at the apex is larger simply because the signal is weaker due to the distance and the gap appears much larger.

Figure 1.2: Fin whale calls recorded on the Svalbard fibre. Left: 4 strong signals with a small narrow gap in signal strength at the apex, and 3 faint weaker calls (prior to call 1, after call 2 and after call 4). Right: 5 calls (apex at 7.4 km) showing a larger gap around the apex, caused by a larger crossline distance between the whale and the fibre.

This gap is caused by the effect of zero strain for normal incidence of an acoustic (P-wave) source in water close to a seabed fibre. The directivity effect of a monopole acoustic source is given by Näsholm et al., 2022:

$$D_x = \cos^2 \theta \quad (1)$$

Where D_x denotes the directivity for the measured horizontal strain and θ is the angle between the acoustic wave and the fibre. If we include geometrical spreading and use a cartesian coordinates the geometrical spreading is given as

$$R = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2} \quad (2)$$

Where x is the offset along the cable, y the crossline distance and z the water depth (or more precisely the vertical distance from the source to the fibre). Combining the directivity effect and the geometrical spreading, we find that the amplitude signal measured by the DAS interrogator (A_x) is given as

$$A_x = \cos^2 \theta / R = \frac{x^2}{(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)^{3/2}} \quad (3)$$

Figure 3 shows clearly that when the crossline distance between the source and the fibre is increased, the amplitude level decreases (red solid line in Figure 3), and the gap at the apex or zero offset increases significantly. These effects are also observed in Figure 2 and explains the typical signal generated by for instance a vocalizing whale (or ship) on a horizontal fibre at the seabed: close to zero signal at apex, then increasing to a maximum and decreasing again after a maxima that is determined by the geometry and directivity effects.

Figure 1.3: Modeled strain assuming the acoustic source at crossline distance zero ($y=0$) and at 1000 m (red solid line). The water depth is 300 m in this case. Notice the reduced amplitude level as well as the broadening of the gap at zero offset.

If the wave hitting the fibre is a shear wave (for instance generated by an earthquake) the directivity equation is very different (Näsholm et al., 2022):

$$D_x^S = \sin 2\theta \quad (4)$$

This means that the strain signal changes sign at zero offset (polarity shift) and that the amplitude variation for an S-wave becomes (after including $1/R$ for geometrical spreading):

$$A_x^S = \sin 2\theta / R = \frac{2x\sqrt{y^2 + z^2}}{(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (5)$$

Figure 4 shows the abrupt polarity change at zero offset and that this change becomes less sharp as the crossline distance increases. In the case of a surface wave (for instance a Rayleigh wave or a Scholte wave) the geometrical spreading has to be replaced by one over square-root of R , and then R is the distance along the seabed from the source to the apex point at the fibre.

Figure 1.4: Modeled strain for an S-wave recorded by a horizontal fibre at the seabed, assuming the elastic source is directly below the fibre at crossline distance zero ($y=0$) and at 1000 m (red solid line). The vertical distance from the source (below the seabed) is 300 m in this case. Notice the reduced amplitude level as well as the broadening of the gap at zero offset.

Figure 1.5: Das recording from an onshore experiment showing the polarity reversal of the Rayleigh wave at zero offset. The source is a hammer sledge that was displaced 1 m (in the crossline distance) from the fibre optic cable. The colored lines illustrates various velocities for the shear wave reflection (SS-event) from the base of the clay layer in this case. The Rayleigh wave is the narrow cone emerging from zero offset (actually around 100 m distance in this case).

Figure 1.6: Modeled strain corresponding to the directivity pattern of a Rayleigh wave similar to the field data shown in Figure 5.

1.3 Ghost effects (Lloyds Mirror effect)

An acoustic source that emits signals at a given depth (z_s) will create a source ghost effect (Lloyds mirror effect) since the acoustic signal is perfectly (assuming a flat horizontal water-air interface) reflected and polarity shifted when the signal reaches the sea surface. Mathematically this effect can be expressed as a sine-function in the frequency domain (see Landrø and Amundsen, 2018 for details):

$$A_x = \frac{2x^2}{(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)^{3/2}} \left| \sin \left(\frac{2\pi f z_s z}{c \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}} \right) \right| \quad (6)$$

Where f is the temporal frequency, z_s is the source depth and θ the angle of incidence. c is the sound velocity in water. Modeled responses including the source ghost effect are shown in Figure X for source depths of 10 and 30 m, respectively, using a dominant frequency of 20 Hz. 20 Hz is the dominant low tone frequency for fin whale calls (Romagosa et al., 2024). We notice that the 30 m signal is significantly stronger than the 10 m source depth signal. This effect is mainly due to the

source ghost effect. If we increase the source frequency to 130 Hz (typical for the overtone of the fin whale call; Romagosa et al., 2024), we notice a significant change in the directivity response (Figure X); rapid variations in the signal strength and more variations as the sources depth increases. This discontinuous response versus offset makes it harder to observe this high frequency tone on fibre optic seabed cable data. In addition to this, the overtone is typically significantly weaker than the dominant 20 Hz tone for fin whales. Another effect that further reduces the amplitudes at 130 Hz is the gauge effect that will be discussed in the following section.

Figure 1.7: Modeled strain response including the strain directivity, geometrical spreading and the ghost directivity effect for a source at 10 and 30 m, respectively. The water depth is 300 m, the frequency is 20 Hz and the crossline distance is zero.

Figure 1.8: Modeled strain response including the strain directivity, geometrical spreading and the ghost directivity effect for a source at 10 and 30 m, respectively. The water depth is 300 m, the frequency is 130 Hz and the crossline distance is zero.

1.4 The Gauge length

A DAS interrogator needs multiple backscattering (Rayleigh backscattering) to create a signal that is above a certain signal to noise threshold. In the interrogator such multiple time-variant signals are averaged over a time window, and this corresponds to a certain length of the fibre; the gauge length (G). This length can be determined by the operator of the interrogator and should be chosen with care related to the objectives of the DAS experiment. Näsholm et al. 2022 gives an approximate expression for the frequency amplitude response (A_G) versus gauge length (G):

$$A_G = \frac{1}{G} \left| \frac{\sin(\pi G f / c)}{\pi f / c} \right| \quad (7)$$

Where c denotes the velocity of the medium. Figure 6 below shows an example for $c=1500$ m/s and gauge lengths of 4 and 8 m. According to equation 6 there is a notch (zero response) for the following frequencies (when the argument of the sine function is equal to $n\pi$):

$$f_n = \frac{nc}{G}, \quad (8)$$

where n is a positive integer and c is the medium velocity.

Figure 1.9: Amplitude response for 4 m (black line) and 8 m (red line) gauge lengths versus frequency assuming a medium velocity of 1500 m/s.

In practice, the gauge length is normally decided by trial and error testing, however strongly guided by the considerations given above. It is always a balance between avoiding these notches and

achieving a sufficient number of backscattered signals for averaging to achieve a reasonable signal to noise ratio.

1.5 Experimental air gun data and frequency effects

A single airgun was used to test the Svalbard fibre sensitivity. A single shot is shown in Figure 1.10, where we can observe strong signals close to the apex. In this case there is a signal also at zero offset (corresponding to approximately 15 km in distance). As expected, the amplitude level increases for larger offset and reaches a maximum followed by a decay around 500 m. We also notice several refracted events where we estimate wave velocities around 2500 m/s.

Figure 1.10: Single air gun shot directly over the fibre optic cable. We notice a sharp decrease at zero offset (approximately at 15 000 m). Notice the weak refraction that split off at approximately 10.5 s. The data has been bandpass-filtered between 15-30 Hz.

Figure 1.11 shows the same air gun shot for a frequency band between 110 and 140 Hz. As expected, the signal strength is significantly reduced compared to the low frequency (15-30 Hz) version. We can

observe that the refracted signals are not visible, and that the gap at zero offset is wider, as expected (see directivity modelling above). Amplitude spectra for selected traces at zero offset (apex) and 250 m offset to each side are shown in Figure 1.12. For low frequencies (10-50 Hz) we observe that the air gun signal is above the background noise level. The theoretical directivity curves give zero response for zero offset. However, in measurements like this we can observe this especially when the distance to the cable is short.

For small offsets ($x \ll z$) the directivity is approximately given as x^2/z^2 . If we assume that the product of this directivity term and the ratio between the wavelength and the gauge length should be greater than a certain threshold a_0 to be above the noise threshold one finds:

Figure 1.11: Single air gun shot directly over the fibre optic cable. We notice a sharp decrease at zero offset (approximately at 15 000 m). Notice the weak refraction that split off at approximately 10.5 s. The data has been bandpass-filtered between 110-140 Hz.

Figure 1.12: Frequency amplitude spectra of selected traces from the air gun shot shown in Figure 1.10. Top spectrum shows the trace at apex (zero offset), middle trace shows the spectrum at 250 m left of apex and the bottom trace shows the spectrum for a trace at 250 m to the right of apex. Notice that there is a signal above noise level for the band between 15 and 50 Hz. For larger offsets this band is as expected much wider and we observe signals above the noise level up to 150 Hz.

The periodicity in the frequency spectra for the air gun signal is given by the bubble period for the 20 cubic inch airgun. In section 2.2 we estimate that the bubble time period for this air gun fired at a depth of 3.5 m is 16 Hz, giving maxima in the frequency spectrum at 16 Hz, 32 Hz, 48 Hz, ... If we compare this to Figure 1.12, we see that this fits reasonably well with the measured DAS-data. In addition to the bubble time period, the frequency content of an air gun signal is dependent on several other parameters, like the water depth, the design of the air gun, the source depth and the direction (see the discussion on ghost effect in section 1.3).

A phenomenological approximation to estimate to what extent DAS-data actually can measure non-zero signals at zero offset (contradicting the cosinesquared directivity), is to assume that the gaugelength will include non-zero offset arrivals that contribute to the signal, and hence give rise to the non-zero amplitude we observe in for instance Figure 1.12. If we assume that the directivity factor multiplied with the acoustic wavelength divided by the gaugelength should be larger than a given number a_0 as follows:

$$\frac{x^2 \lambda}{z^2 G} > a_0, \quad (9)$$

We can use this to estimate how the cutoff-frequency f_c varies as function of distance between the source and the fibre optic cable (z). Letting x be equal to the GL we find that the wavelength should be greater than

$$\lambda > \frac{a_0 z^2}{G}, \quad (10)$$

or alternatively that the frequency should be less than

$$f_c < \frac{cG}{a_0 z^2}. \quad (11)$$

Figure 1.13 shows how this cut-off frequency varies with water depth for a cable deployed at the seabed. The constant a_0 depends on the source strength and probably also how the fibre is embedded and coupled to the seabed.

It is important to note that this formula is phenomenological and that the threshold constant a_0 varies with source strength and of course background noise level. Needless to say that the value we have used in Figure 1.13 has been adapted to fit with our observations in Figure 1.12. It is important to note that an irregular seabed topography will create Scholtewaves at the seabed, that might also lead to low-frequency energy at zero offset. This effect is expected to vary from shot to shot, depending on the seabed characteristics.

Figure 1.13: Minimum frequency versus water depth for detection of DAS signals at zero offset. The gaugelength is 8 m and the threshold constant $a_0 = 0.005 \text{ m}^{-1}$ in the current example. For a depth of 200 m we find that all frequencies less than 50 Hz should be detectable in this case.

The directional sensitivity is further examined using airgun shot at time 14:55:29 and location 505642.2 8689202.5. This shot was chosen and further examined since it yielded asymmetrical results. Figure 1.14 shows the seismogram of this shot after applying a bandpass filter and time decimation.

Figure 1.14: Time domain seismogram in strain-rate after applying a bandpass filter between 5 Hz – 200 Hz and applying a time domain decimation factor of 2. The apex of the first arrival is at a fibre length of approximately 15636 m. Note that there is a gap in the first arrival, similar to Figure 1.11.

When we convert the time domain to the frequency domain of the raw shot, we obtain Figure 1.15. Here, the apex becomes clearly visible. It is worth noting that a V-shaped pattern appears near the apex in the frequency domain. It appears that higher frequencies have a larger amplitude near the apex. Conversely, lower frequencies have a higher amplitude further away from the apex. This V-shaped pattern is only visible for about 350 m in fibre length on each side of the apex. After this first V-shape, there appears to be a gap in the higher frequencies, followed by an increase in high frequency amplitudes again. The second increase in high frequency amplitudes appears to be asymmetrical. Figure 1.15 shows that the second increase on the left of the apex is between fibre length 14300 m and 14700 m. On the right it starts around 16750 m till 17300 m. Interestingly enough, the second increase in high frequency amplitudes on the right side of the apex starts at a farther distance from the apex and illuminates a larger section of the fibre compared to the left side. Here, we can identify the first asymmetrical result. Additionally, converting to the space-frequency domain helps us to identify background or system noise. Figure 1.15. We can observe system or background noise around 46, 92 and 126 Hz. We know this

is noise due to the narrow band width and the very similar amplitudes across the entire section.

Figure 1.15: Frequency domain of the raw strain-rate shot. Note that the apex is also clearly visible. Additionally, a V-shaped pattern appears. Higher frequencies seem are recorded closer to the apex, whereas lower frequencies become more dominant at larger distances.

We can also quantify the difference in apparent velocity related to the asymmetry. This can be done by transforming the data to the frequency-wavenumber domain. By doing this, we obtain Figure 1.16. We first observe the asymmetry between the negative and positive wavenumber patterns, meaning between wave move towards the interrogator, the negative wavenumbers, and waves moves away from the interrogator, the positive wavenumbers. The negative wavenumbers show clear quarter hyperbolas, whereas the positive wavenumbers show more distorted hyperbolas.

When we zoom in on the FK domain, and select the slowest linear event for both the positive and negative wavenumber, we obtain Figure 1.17. We observe that the lowest arrival, the direct P-wave arrival, has a velocity of 1664 ms^{-1} for the negative wavenumbers. The positive wavenumber shows a slower first arrival of 1545 ms^{-1} . This 7.7 % difference can partly be explained by the fibre layout, since the first arrival will always be traveling through seawater. Potentially, some difference in salinity and water temperature can change the p-wave velocity in the water, however, this is unlikely to explain a difference in velocity of 7.7 %. It is therefore believed that the difference in velocity is mostly due to the curvature of the cable, giving a difference in apparent velocity. Additionally, bright spots at an

increment of 15.15 Hz can be seen, which are related to the airgun. More information about this phenomenon will be given in section 2.2

Figure 1.16: Frequency-wavenumber domain of the bandpass and decimated shot. that the negative wave numbers show clearer hyperbolas than the right side.

Figure 1.17: Frequency-wavenumber domain like Figure 1.16 but zoomed in and with a marker at the slowest event. On the left the marker is set at the negative wavenumber, and on the right it is set at the positive wavenumber. Note there is a velocity difference of 7.7 %.

Finally, when we look at individual traces in both the time and frequency domain, we observe a large discrepancy and again the asymmetry in the data, as shown in Figure 1.18. In this figure, a channel at the apex of Figure 1.14 was selected, channel 1159 at fibre length 15636 m, followed by channels 1097 and 1221 at fibre length 15388 m and 15884 m, respectively, both 248 m away from the apex. What is interesting in this figure is the apex does not show a clear first arrival, but does show clear reverberations after the first arrival, starting after 0.08 s after the interpolated first arrival. The amplitudes appear to be slightly higher than the noise. Only when looking at the Fast Fourier

Transform (FFT), we can observe a clear difference in the low frequencies < 30 Hz. This is also confirmed in Figure 1.15. When we look at the channels 248 m to the left and right of the apex, we can see a clear arrival at 0.16 s. The delay is caused due the add path length from the airgun to the fibre located 248 m from the apex. It is striking that the time domain for the channels with a 248 m offset from the apex show a clear first arrival and the FFT results show much larger amplitudes for high frequencies. This is contrasted by apex channel with a lack of a first arrival, and an increase in amplitude of the lower frequencies.

Figure 1.18: Top three figures show the time domain for strain-rate data for channels 1159, 1097 and 1221. These channels are at the apex of Figure 1.14, 248 m to the left of the apex, and 248 m to the right of the apex, respectively. Note that the scale is different per plot.

Additionally, we can create the same result in strain rather than strain-rate by integrating the results of Figure 1.14. This way, we convert Figure 1.14 into Figure 1.19. By integrating the data, we boost the lower frequencies, creating a difference in the frequency spectrum. This can be seen when comparing Figure 1.18 to Figure 1.20. When comparing the strain-rate amplitudes and frequencies of Figure 1.18 with strain amplitudes and frequencies of Figure 1.20 it is evident that there is an increase in higher frequency amplitudes for strain-rate, and a decrease in lower frequency amplitudes.

Figure 1.19: Time domain seismogram in strain after applying a bandpass filter between 5 Hz – 200 Hz and applying a time domain decimation factor of 2. The apex of the first arrival is at a fibre length of approximately 15636 m. Note that there is a gap in the first arrival, similar to Figure 1.11 and 1.14

Figure 1.20: Top three figures show the time domain for strain data for channels 1159, 1097 and 1221. These channels are at the apex of Figure 1.14, 248 m to the left of the apex, and 248 m to the right of the apex, respectively. Note that the scale is different per plot.

2 The DAS field laboratory at Svalbard

2.1 The fibre optic cables between Ny-Ålesund and Longyearbyen, Svalbard

The fibre optic cables connecting Ny-Ålesund and Longyearbyen at Svalbard were deployed in 2015 by SIKT on behalf of the Norwegian Government. Figure 1 shows a map of the fibre optic cables and the water depth profile, and Figure 2 shows a 3D perspective view of the cable track seen from Northern Svalbard towards South. The fibre is trenched up to 1-2 m below seabed where there are sediments covering the seabed and placed directly on solid bed rock when there is no sediment coverage. This will impact coupling effects for DAS acquisition that will be discussed in proceeding sections in this report. For the Submerse project, we have installed an interrogator in Ny-Ålesund, and this interrogator has recorded data practically continuously since June 2022.

Figure 2.1: Map of the two fibre optic cables connecting Ny-Ålesund and Longyearbyen at Svalbard. The length of each cable is approximately 250 km, and the maximum water depth is around 400 m.

Figure 2.2: Perspective view showing one of the fibre optic cable tracks (black line) as seen from Northern Svalbard towards South. Figure modified from Norsk Polarinstitutt.

The first interrogator was installed in Ny Ålesund on 2nd June 2022, and has been recording data continuously since then, apart from some technical breaks. Photos showed in figures 9 and 10 are taken during the DAS-installation in 2022. In 2024 we made several days of recorded data from this interrogator available to the SUBMERSE team. The length of recording varies from approximately 60 to 135 km. The gauge length has primarily been kept to 8 m, but some recent data has been recorded using 2, 4 and 16 m gauge length. As for the temporal sampling it varies from 625 Hz to 200 Hz depending on the signals being recorded. The first 1.5 years recordings were at 625 Hz to understand and capture the majority of the signals present along the fibre. After we mapped out these signals we were able to tune the sampling rate accordingly, which also helps decrease the data load. We are currently working together with SIKT and UiB to establish a transmission line of a single DAS-channel from offshore Svalbard so that real-time seismological data can be shared with Submerse partners through the EIDA node hosted by UiB. ASN, GFZ and GeoAzur have already been using such a procedure and the current process is to adapt it to our use case. In 2024 (September 12th) Alcalá university installed a low-frequency interrogator in Ny-Ålesund that has been recording continuously apart from the period December 3rd to 5th. It will continue recording until March 2025. The measuring length is 50 km and the sampling rate is 20 samples per second for a gauge length of 10 m. UiB installed 3 seabed seismometers in the vicinity of the cable we are interrogating by DAS in 2024, one close to the inner cable and two close to the outer cable. These are laid out as a triangle to facilitate for various array processing procedures. Work to compare and analyse the DAS and seismometer data has not started yet.

Figure 2.3: Kristina Skarvang connecting the fibre from the interrogator to the seabottom fibre connecting Ny-Ålesund and Longyearbyen (2nd June 2022).

Figure 2.4: The interrogator in the instrument room in Ny Ålesund.

2.2 The air gun test along the two Svalbard fibre optic cables

In 2022 a dedicated test using a single 40 cubic inch air gun was conducted along the inner cable and crossing over to the outer cable at the last part of the test trajectory. Figure 2.5 shows the shooting line relative to the two fibres. The figure also shows estimations of the shooting vessel's position using two different estimation methods (see Rørstadbotnen et al., 2023). The source depth was 3.5 m.

Figure 2.5: Shooting line (solid thick line that is color-coded according to time) and two estimation methods for the shot positions (Grid Search and Bayes-type estimation). We notice that most estimations are within an accuracy of approximately 100 m. Figure from Rørstadbotnen et al., 2023.

We don't have a measured value for the bubble time period of this airgun. However, from Langhammer et al., 1995, a measurement of a 40 cubic inch air gun fired at 3 m has a bubble time period of 83 ms. If we use equation 1 in Landrø, 2014, we find that this period for a 20 cubic inch air gun should be $0.5^{1/3}=0.79$ times the bubble time period for an air gun of the double volume (40 cubic inch), corresponding to 66 ms. In addition to this we need to correct for the fact that the 20 cubic inch air gun is fired at a depth of 3.5 m instead of 3 m. Using equation 1 again to correct for this minor difference in source depth, the bubble time period should be scaled by 0.97, yielding an estimated bubble time period of 64 ms. Finally a correction for colder water at Svalbard compared to the fjord in Norway where the 40 cubic inch air gun measurements were done is needed. A reasonable assumption is that this difference is of the order of 8 K. Using equation 3 in Landrø, 2014, we find a correction of only -0.4 ms, which is negligible. Hence we conclude that a reasonable estimate for the bubble time period is 64 ms, yielding maximum frequencies at $1000/64 = 16$ Hz, 32 Hz, 48 Hz, 64 Hz,... We will use this estimate to interpret the frequency spectra obtained from the field experiment.

2.3 An interesting observation: A refracted P-wave generating a Scholte wave at the seabed.

Figure 2.6 shows a very interesting wave that are rarely observed for seismic data. We observe a double Scholte-wave event observed prior to the arrival of the direct P-wave arrival. This double event is weak, but clearly observable. We notice the typical polarity reversal at the apex (see for instance Figure 1.4). This double event is generated by a refracted P-wave (also weak in the figure) propagating with an apparent velocity of 3000 m/s. The distance between the two (propagating with a velocity of 1250 m/s) is approximately 20 m (Figure 2.7). Furthermore, we notice that the two Scholte waves are regenerated by the direct P-wave arrival, generating much stronger Scholte waves. We interpret this as caused by a graben structure in the seabed, with a width of approximately 20 m. The water depth is approximately 180 m in this area and the distance from the apex (shot position) to the point where the refracted P-wave splits off from the direct P-wave is approximately 200 m (hard to determine precisely). Using Snell's law for critical angle yields a velocity for the first layer below the seabed of approximately 2240 m/s, which is significantly less than the estimated 3000 m/s for the interpreted refracted event.

Figure 2.6: Single air gun shot fired at approximately 24.95 km. Notice the weak Scholte waves (SH1 and SH2) generated by a weak refracted wave (shown by a dashed marked by 3000 m/s). The Scholte wave propagation velocity is approximately 1250 m/s.

Figure 2.7: Zoom of the two Scholte waves 24420 m and 24440 m clearly showing the polarity shift that is characteristic for shear waves and Scholte waves.

Figure 2.8 shows how the seismic wave(ray) generated by the air gun source propagates from the water layer (1) into the sedimentary layer (2). At the interface between the sedimentary layer and the underlying bedrock layer (3) a refracted wave is generated when the incidence angle is equal to or larger than the critical angle. This refracted wave propagates with the P-wave velocity of layer 3, and will therefore reach the farther distances on the fibre prior to the direct arrival of the P-wave propagating in the water layer. At some distance it will also arrive earlier than the refracted seabed wave. Using ray-theory the travelttime for a refracted wave from the interface between layer 2 and 3 in the model shown in Figure 2.8 is given as:

$$T_R = \frac{z_1}{v_1 \cos \theta_1} + \frac{2z_2}{v_2 \cos \theta_2} + \frac{x - z_1 \tan \theta_1 - 2z_2 \tan \theta_2}{v_3} \quad (12)$$

This can be simplified to

$$T_R = \frac{x}{v_3} + \frac{z_1 \cos \theta_1}{v_1} + \frac{2z_2 \cos \theta_2}{v_2} \quad (13)$$

Figure 2.9 shows the direct arrival (black solid line), the refracted event from the base of the sediment layer (red solid line) and the refracted event from the seabed (black dashed line). From the field data observation we do not observe the refracted event from the seabed, but the refracted event from the sediment-bedrock interface is visible (although weak). In the same area we have used active earthquakes in the area to estimate the shear wave velocity in the sediment layer (Taweessintananon et al., 2024). From these results (Figure 2.10) we observe that the shear wave velocity is gradually increasing with depth within the sediment layer. It is reasonable to assume that the P-wave velocity will also increase with depth, indicating that the refracted wave will be weaker since the contrast to the water P-wave velocity (1500 m/s) is moderate, in contrast to the sediment-bedrock interface where this contrast is stronger. In the modelled example in Figure 2.9, we have used the following parameters: water depth: 180 m, thickness of sediment layer: 20 m; velocity of the three layers: 1500 m/s, 2000 m/s and 3000 m/s, respectively.

Figure 2.8: Sketch showing a possible ray-paths for the refractive wave (red solid line) and how that is measured on separate locations at the seabed fibre (black triangles). The distance to the first refracted wave recorded at the fibre is x . Layer 1 is the water layer (z_1) and layer 2 is the sedimentary layer with velocities v_1 and v_2 , respectively. Underlying the sedimentary layer there is the bedrock layer with velocity v_3 which is significantly higher than the velocity of the sedimentary layer. When the refracted wavefront hits a seabed inhomogeneity there is a potential for generating a Scholtewave at the seabed interface. θ_2 is the critical angle ($\sin \theta_2 = v_2 / v_3$) for the ray being refracted from the interface between layers 2 and 3.

Figure 2.9: Modelled traveltimes versus offset for direct arrival at seabed (black solid line), refracted event at the water-sediment interface (dashed black line) and refracted event from the sediment-bedrock interface (red solid line). The water depth is 180 m, the thickness of the sediment layer is 20 m, and the velocities for the water layer, sediment layer and the bedrock layer are 1500 m/s, 2000 m/s and 3000 m/s, respectively.

Figure 2.10: Estimated thickness and S-wave velocity of the sediment-layer exploiting resonance effects caused by an earthquake in the Isfjord, Svalbard. Notice that the sediment layer is very thin for the area around 25 km. Figure from Taweasantanon et al., 2024.

Taweasantanon et al. (2024) used shear wave resonances generated within the sediment layer to estimate thickness and the shearwave velocity gradient (Figure 2.10). We notice that the thickness of the sediment layer is thin (10-20 m thickness). This might explain why the critical offset occurring at a distance of 200 m from the apex has a corresponding P-wave velocity of 2240 m/s and that the velocity of the underlying basalt layer is 3000 m/s.

3 Coupling effects related to trenching of cable and geology

The DAS-signal recorded on a trenched seabed cable varies as the geology is changing and especially when the cable is buried (Figure 3.1) and surrounded by sediments or is laid directly on bedrock.

Figure 3.1: Illustrating when the fibre cables are buried in sediments (green) and when they are laid directly on bedrock (red). Notice that most of the area outside Prin Karls Forland is a bedrock shelf that is shallower than most of the other areas.

Figure 3.2 is a good example of such variations, where we observe that the P-wave arrival is much weaker and irregular in areas where the cable is laid directly on the bedrock compared to the locations where the cable is buried. We observe a clear correlation between buried and not-buried cable. The presence of sediments acts as an amplifier for earthquake signals. This effect has been observed previously, see for instance Figure 3.3 that is taken from Landrø et al., 2022, supplemental information. We observe the same effect in Figure 3.2 at both ends of the fibre where the P-wave signals are much weaker compared to the buried cable. At each end of the fibre (both close to Ny-Ålesund and Longyearbyen the fibre is trenched at land (onshore) and is not connected to a sedimentary layer as for the offshore parts of the cable. Hence for the first kilometres of the cable we observe weak (but still stronger) signals compared to the stretches where the fibre is trenched into the seabed. A more detailed look at the part of the fibre where it is not trenched (marked by a red solid line in Figure 3.2) reveals that there are significant variations in the amplitude level going from low for the first 20 km of the non-buried cable stretch to higher amplitudes for the last part. This is interpreted as variable coupling that could be coupled to the topography or the presence of thin sediments (of the order of centimetres) leading to increased coupling for the latter part.

Figure 3.2: RMS-amplitude for a 6.5 MW earthquake West of Svalbard measured at one interrogator in Ny-Ålesund (left) and at another interrogator located in Longyearbyen (right). The right DAS-signals have been mirrored to mimic the effect of continuous recording along the fibre from Ny-Ålesund to Longyearbyen. The black-red line below the RMS-plot shows where the cable is buried in sediments (black) and where it is laid directly on bedrock.

Figure 3.3: Example of a teleseismic earthquake ($M_{ww}=7.8$) in Alaska on 22nd July 2020 recorded at the Svalbard fibre optic cable in an area where the cable is buried in sediments. Notice the strong P-wave event compared to the relative weak P-wave event on the seismometer-data recorded on-shore Svalbard (bottom panel). Figure from Landrø et al., 2022.

For a trenched or buried cable the surrounding material is very important for the response and coupling effects. Taweessintananon et al., 2024 discuss this in detail and suggests that the shear-wave resonance effect causes systematic changes that are observed both in the space-time domain as well as in the space-frequency domain. Figure 3.4 shows that as the thickness of the sediment column is thinning from 250 to 200 km and from approximately 190 km the fibre is lying directly on bedrock. We observe that the signal gets somewhat weaker as the thickness of the sediments is decreasing, and significantly weaker in the area between 130-200 km. In Figure 3.4 we can trace the earthquake signal from 250 km to approximately 180 km where the noise level increases significantly. Furthermore, we notice that for areas where low frequency ocean gravity waves are present, for instance between 220 and 225 km and around 200 km, these signals (coming from above) have a good coupling. Ocean gravity waves are observed as dipping (and often crossing) events that can be observed also prior to the earthquake in Figure 3.4 a.

Figure 3.4: Frequency analysis of the DAS data recorded during a strong earthquake. Top figure shows conventional time versus position data for 1200 seconds, and the earthquake signal is marked by the P, S arrow on the left. Middle plot shows frequency versus distance for the same time interval. The red dashed lines represent interpretation of the first and second shear wave resonances, respectively. Bottom: Estimated shear velocity profile and thickness of sediment column. Figure taken from Taweasintananon et al. (2024).

A more detailed example of ocean gravity waves is shown in Figure 3.5 where we clearly see different slopes of the events in a time-distance DAS plot. The cable is turning from being east-west oriented

prior to 60 km into being north-south oriented beyond 60 km (see Figure 3.1 and be aware that the distance in Figure 3.5 is measured from Ny Ålesund and not Longyearbyen as for Figure 3.1). In Figure 3.5 we furthermore observe (between 54 and 60 km) the influence of the southern tidal current.

Figure 3.5: DAS-data filtered from 0.01-0.4 Hz taken from the area where the fibre is turning South and climbs up to the plateau where the cable is laid directly on bedrock (around 59 km). We notice that the Northerly wind is clearly exposed on the fibre and mixes with the tidal current flow coming from the opposite direction (South).

Comparing for instance Figure 3.5 and Figure 3.2 illustrates that there is a huge difference between energy arising from the interior of the earth (Figure 3.2) and acoustic energy being generated in the water layer (Figures 3.4 and 3.5). For signals being generated in the water layer, the coupling seems to be much better even when the cable is not trenched compared to when the energy comes from below. Here it should be noticed that the dipping events observed between 60 and 64 km in Figure 3.5 could also be related to rugging of the fibre at the seabed caused by the Northerly wind generated ocean gravity wave rather than direct coupling between the acoustic wave generated by the ocean gravity wave.

To further investigate the coupling effects we focused our analysis on the airgun shots in Isfjorden, as well as an earthquake recorded on the same fiber segment. We use the known shot position of the airgun (i.e., a known shot position) and the known fiber position to find the virtual channel at three different positions from the source. The three distances used were 300 m, 500 m and 700 m. The

processing is done in four steps; (1) the channel number at the wanted distance from the source is estimated using the Pythagorean distance between the source and the channel position. The channel corresponding to the wanted distance can then be extracted. (2) Band-pass filter the data between 10 and 120 Hz to focus on the dominant energy in the recorded data. (3) Use the short-term-average over long-term-average algorithm (STA/LTA, from ObsPY) to find consistent triggers where the energy arrives on the interesting channel. (4) Based on the STA/LTA define a window used to compute a root-mean-square average of the first break. A window length of 0.05 s was used to only pick out energy from the first break, hence excluding the following reverberations.

Figure 3.6 to 3.8 show the obtained RMS levels as a function of channel distance. Two channels were picked for each shot, both at the same distance from the source but at different sides of the shot. As expected, a decrease in amplitude is observed for increasing distance from the source. The RMS signature varies for the different distances, indicating that several factors need to be considered to fully understand the data, not only the coupling. These factors include but are not limited to the incidence angle of the wave and the bathymetry profile. For 300 m distance there is a clear correlation between the fiber cable water depth and the RMS of the first arriving wave. It is, however, not clear whether this effect is due to change in incidence angle or due to the shape of the bathymetry. Further analysis is needed to better understand these effects. For the other two profiles the water depth of the fiber seems to affect the RMS level to a lower degree, i.e., the profiles are relatively constant. Moreover, for the 700 m offset we see additional arrivals before the direct wave, probably the refracted wave overtaking the direct wave.

We further zoom in on the area with relatively flat bathymetry in Figure 3.8 (between 14300 m and 20000 m from the interrogator) and observe a much more stable RMS response. The highest variation (max value of smoothed curves to the minimum value of the smoothed curves) of 34%. All other values are lower than this percentage.

Figure 3.6: RMS values for channels 300 m away from the source for 120 airgun shots. The gray line indicates the water depth of the fiber; the red lines the signal ahead of the ship (towards the mouth of the fjord); the blue lines the signal behind the ship (towards Longyearbyen); the black lines the signal at the apex of the shot signal.

Figure 3.7: RMS values for channels 500 m away from the source for 120 airgun shots. The gray line indicates the water depth of the fiber; the red lines the signal ahead of the ship (towards the mouth of the fjord); the blue lines the signal behind the ship (towards Longyearbyen); the black lines the signal at the apex of the shot signal.

Figure 3.8: RMS values for channels 700 m away from the source for 120 airgun shots. The gray line indicates the water depth of the fiber; the red lines the signal ahead of the ship (towards the mouth of the fjord); the blue lines the signal behind the ship (towards Longyearbyen); the black lines the signal at the apex of the shot signal.

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Figure 3.9: RMS values for channels 300 m away from the source. Zoomed version of Figure 3.5 focusing on the area with flat bathymetry. The variation in RMS is very consistent over this range, with the maximum value being 34% higher than the minimum value- The gray line indicates the water depth of the fiber; the red lines the signal ahead of the ship (towards the mouth of the fjord); the blue lines the signal behind the ship (towards Longyearbyen).

We can apply a similar approach for an earthquake. We pick an earthquake recorded on the 9th of September 2022 at 09:19:27 UTC. We convert the data to strain-rate, bandpass filter and decimate the data in time to obtain Figure 3.10. This Figure clearly shows that we do not have a clear first arrival, unlike the airgun data. Therefore, we select a time window of 60 s instead of 0.05 s for the earthquake RMS values. Since we have a longer time window, we will also include the RMS values of ambient noise to help identify high background noise anomalies. The first RMS results of the entire seismogram in Figure 3.10 is shown in Figure 3.11. Here, we can see the RMS values oscillating, and we observe a large increase in the background noise RMS values after 110 km. This is related to the limited light budget left in the fibre. Additionally, we can observe a similar behavior in RMS value oscillations between the airgun data, and the earthquake data. First, we observe lower and more stable RMS values in the sections of 14000 - 21000 m, like Figure 3.7 and 3.9. Second, we can see an increase, followed by a decrease, followed by an increase again in RMS at the section 21000 – 26000 m, similar to Figure 3.7.

In conclusion, the coupling effect is not straightforward to estimate using the proposed methodology and further improvement is needed. We do, however, see valuable trends in the data that indicates the path forward.

Figure 3.10: Time domain data in strain-rate of the selected earthquake recorded on the 9th of September 2022 at 09:19:27 UTC. Note how the difference in the first arrival, the p-wave, and the second arrival, the s-wave can easily be followed over the entire 123 km length of the seismogram.

Figure 3.11: RMS values of a 60 s equivalent dataset (background noise; blue) and 60 s of earthquake signal (red). The background noise dramatically increase after 110 km due to the limited light budget left in the fibre.

Figure 3.12: RMS values of a 60 s equivalent dataset and 60 s of earthquake signal. The normalized RMS values dramatically increase after 110 km due to the limited light budget left in the fibre. This figure is a zoom in of Figure 3.11, showing more stable RMS values for the 14000 – 21000 m fibre section, compared to the values from 21000 m onwards

2 DAS-repeating systems for long range monitoring

There are several vendors working on new methods for enhancing the length for DAS-interrogation significantly by developing DAS-repeaters similar to the conventional repeaters that are used for telecommunication for long seabed fibre optic cables. Figure 4.1 shows an example from a research and development project carried out by Alcatel Submarine Networks (ASN); Brenne, 2024. As we have seen in previous sections, the typical length where we can expect DAS-signals with good S/N-ratio is of the order of 100 km. For long cables crossing for instance oceans like the Pacific or the Atlantic, alternative sparse recording using the conventional repeaters as recording devices (Matta et al. 202x) is an alternative, but will not give detailed information at the same level as DAS-recording.

Figure 4.1: A conceptual set up for superlong DAS-acquisition using multiple DAS-interrogators and DAS-repeaters along the fibre. (Figure from ASN)

In a recent laboratory test ASN showed that it was possible to detect high quality signals at the end 54 km long fibre passing through 37 repeater spans, totalling a length of 2227 km, at 1 Hz sampling frequency and with a spatial resolution of 10 m using 39 EDFA repeaters (Rønnekleiv et al., 2024). The Polar Connect project recently launched by NORUnet focus on a long fibre optic cable for telecommunication connecting Europe to Far East Asia. To enable DAS-interrogation for such a fibre optic cable, a system including DAS-repeaters could be a realistic solution. In this way it could be possible to use this fibre for sensing in very remote areas like north of Canada and areas close to the North Pole. For environmental, oceanographic, seismological and other purposes this will create significant and important future research opportunities.

4 Raman and Brillouin interrogators for temperature monitoring

Besides seismic waves, optical fibres can also be used to measure temperature using distributed temperature sensing (DTS) and static strain and temperature (DTSS). DTS uses Raman back scattering and DTSS uses Brillouin backscattering, whereas DAS uses Rayleigh scattering. An overview with the different scattering mechanisms and their intensities is given in Figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1: A schematic overview of the different scattering mechanisms. Raman scattering which changes in intensity due to a temperature change (DTS), Brillouin scattering which changes in frequency f_0 due to temperature or strain (DTSS), and Rayleigh scattering which measures a phase shift due to the altering optical path caused by the contraction or elongation of the optical fibre. (Figure from Lu, Thomas, & Hellevang, 2019)

From Figure 5.1, it follows that DAS has the largest dynamic range due to the highest scattering mechanism. DAS has a dynamic range reported up to 171 km without amplifiers (Waagaard et al., 2021). Single-ended DTSS values then follow with a range up to 100 km (Alahbabi, Cho, & Newson, 2004). Finally, Raman DTS values have been reported up to 70 km by commercial parties.

DTS measurements have been used for measuring the burial depth of power cables (Lux et al., 2018). The range of DTS measurements are often limiting, which is why they can be complemented by relative temperature measurements derived from DAS measurements (Bradly, Haavik & Landro, 2024). However, special care has to be taken into account correlation cable deformation measurements using DAS. Unlike Raman or Brillouin, DAS only provides a temperature change. Nevertheless, due to the superior range of DAS, temperature sensing using DAS is increasing in popularity in recent years (Sidenko et al., 2022).

5 Conclusions

We demonstrate that a conventional telecommunication fibre that was deployed in 2015 offshore Svalbard give high quality and reliable distributed acoustic sensing data for a range of approximately 110 km. We find that theoretical directivity and amplitude equations fit experimental data. For instance, for P-waves we observe a symmetric response close to zero at zero offset that increases to a maximum followed by a somewhat slower decay for larger offsets. For shear waves the characteristic polarity flip at zero offset is observed in several of the examples discussed in this report, and especially for Scholte waves generated at the seabed.

Coupling factors are hard to quantify for these seabed fibre cables. We compare amplitude levels for a dedicated test where a single air gun was used as a source and fired directly above the fibre. We find that the air gun amplitude levels are dependent on seabed topography, near surface geology in addition to varying coupling effect caused by the trenching process and natural variations in the fibre glass structure. Further and more comprehensive analysis is needed to conclude on whether such controlled experiments are well suited for estimating reliable coupling factors for a trenched fibre.

Due to inhomogeneities at the seabed we interpret that a head wave propagating at the interface between the thin sediment layer below the seabed and the underlying bedrock. This head wave (refraction) propagates with a velocity close to 3000 m/s and interacts with a scour in the seabed to create a Scholte wave propagating with a velocity of 1250 m/s.

For the air gun data there is a low but non-zero signal at zero offset. We suggest a simplistic equation to explain this effect, which contradicts the conventional cosine squared directivity for acoustic waves recorded by a fibre optic cable. More work is needed to evaluate if this equation captures the main effects related to water depth, frequency and gauge-length.

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